

1 **Changes in belowground biodiversity during ecosystem development**

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93 **Abstract**

94 Belowground organisms play critical roles in maintaining multiple ecosystem processes, including
95 plant productivity, decomposition, and nutrient cycling. Despite their importance, we have a
96 limited understanding of how and why belowground biodiversity (bacteria, fungi, protists, and
97 invertebrates) may change as soils develop over centuries to millennia (pedogenesis). Moreover,
98 it is unclear whether belowground biodiversity changes during pedogenesis are similar to the
99 patterns observed for aboveground plant diversity. Herein, we evaluated the role of resource
100 availability, nutrient stoichiometry and soil abiotic factors in driving belowground biodiversity
101 across 16 soil chronosequences (from centuries to millennia) spanning a wide range of globally-
102 distributed ecosystem types. Changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis followed
103 two main patterns. In lower productivity ecosystems (drier and colder), increases in belowground
104 biodiversity tracked increases in plant cover. In more productive ecosystems (wetter and warmer),
105 increased acidification during pedogenesis was associated with declines in belowground
106 biodiversity. Changes in the diversity of bacteria, fungi, protists, and invertebrates with
107 pedogenesis were strongly and positively correlated worldwide, highlighting that belowground
108 biodiversity share similar ecological drivers as soils and ecosystems develop. In general, temporal
109 changes in aboveground plant diversity and belowground biodiversity were not correlated,
110 challenging the common perception that belowground biodiversity should follow similar patterns
111 to those of plant diversity during ecosystem development. Together, our findings provide evidence
112 that ecological patterns in belowground biodiversity are predictable across major globally-
113 distributed ecosystem types, and suggest that shifts in plant cover and soil acidification during
114 ecosystem development are associated with changes in belowground biodiversity over centuries
115 to millennia.

116 **Significance Statement**

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118 We do not know how and why belowground biodiversity may change as soils develop over
119 centuries to millennia, hampering our ability to predict the myriad of ecosystem processes
120 regulated by belowground organisms under changing environments. We conducted a global survey
121 of 16 soil chronosequences spanning a wide range of ecosystem types and found that in less
122 productive ecosystems, increases in belowground biodiversity followed increases in plant cover.
123 However, in more productive ecosystems, acidification during soil development was often
124 associated with declines in belowground biodiversity. The biodiversity of multiple soil organisms
125 exhibited similar patterns over time but, in contrast to expectations, changes in plant diversity were
126 not associated with corresponding changes in belowground biodiversity.

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129 **Introduction**

130 Belowground organisms play critical roles in maintaining the rates and stability of multiple
131 ecosystem processes, including plant productivity, decomposition, and nutrient cycling (1-3).
132 Complementary ecological theories have been proposed to explain belowground biodiversity
133 patterns, including theories related to above- and belowground resource availability, nutrient
134 stoichiometry and abiotic environmental factors (1-12; see SI Appendix, Table S1). However, and
135 despite a longstanding interest in the topic (4-8), the patterns in belowground biodiversity as soils
136 develop over centuries to millennia (pedogenesis), and the environmental factors responsible for
137 those patterns, remain largely unresolved. It is also unclear whether belowground biodiversity
138 follows a similar trend to that of plant diversity during pedogenesis (4-6), which often follows a
139 positive or hump-shaped relationship attributed to changes in abiotic environmental factors (e.g.,
140 acidification) and soil resource availability (e.g., soil phosphorus) as soils develop (4-6).
141 Improving our knowledge of the mechanisms driving changes in belowground biodiversity during
142 pedogenesis is critical for predicting both global ecological patterns and the many ecosystem
143 processes regulated by belowground organisms (1-3).

144 There are two main reasons why we lack a mechanistic understanding of how belowground
145 biodiversity changes during pedogenesis. First, studies of belowground biodiversity patterns with
146 pedogenesis have mostly been conducted on a few individual soil chronosequences (13-17), with
147 such work mostly focusing on a single group of belowground organisms such as bacteria (16),
148 fungi (18) or protists (19), or on changes in microbial biomass and community structure (17).
149 Although such studies provide valuable information, pedogenesis often follows different
150 trajectories depending on factors such as soil parent material and climate (7-8,19-21). Moreover,
151 multiple taxa should be considered in concert to achieve a holistic understanding of how
152 belowground biodiversity changes during pedogenesis. Second, most studies to date have focused
153 on changes in belowground biodiversity during initial stages of primary succession (i.e. years to
154 centuries; 13,22), with few studies evaluating effects over much longer time scales (i.e., from
155 centuries to thousands or millions of years; 13,15-16). The fate of belowground biodiversity is
156 expected to differ between early and late stages of pedogenesis because older ecosystems may
157 enter a retrogressive phase (19,24-26). This stage of ecosystem development is typically
158 characterized by reduced resource availability (soil phosphorus [P], carbon [C], and plant
159 biomass), altered soil nutrient stoichiometry (e.g., increased nitrogen [N]:P ratios), and soil
160 acidification (19,23-26), which could change the long-term development of belowground
161 biodiversity.

162 Here, we considered multiple complementary ecological theories, based on above and
163 belowground resource availability, nutrient stoichiometry and abiotic environmental factors (see
164 SI Appendix, Table S1 for details) to identify the predominant mechanisms driving the changes in
165 belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis across ecosystem types (SI Appendix, Material and
166 Methods). To address this, we conducted soil and vegetation surveys across 16 globally-distributed
167 chronosequences, ranging in age from hundreds to millions of years, and encompassing a wide
168 range of climatic conditions (tropical, temperate, continental, polar and arid), vegetation types
169 (grasslands, shrublands, forests and croplands) and chronosequence origins (volcanic,
170 sedimentary, dunes and glacier; SI Appendix, Fig. 1A; Tables S2 and S3). The diversity of soil
171 organisms (bacteria, fungi, protists and invertebrates) was measured via marker gene amplicon

172 sequencing (see SI Appendix, Table S4 for information on the dominant bacterial, fungal, protist,
173 and invertebrate taxa detected).

174 **Results and Discussion**

175 Species richness (i.e., number of phylotypes) and Shannon diversity of soil bacteria, fungi, protists
176 and invertebrates were highly correlated (SI Appendix, Figs S1-S4). Because of this, we used
177 richness as our metric of diversity in further analyses. Importantly, we found that the richness
178 (diversity hereafter) of soil bacteria, fungi, protists and invertebrates across each chronosequence
179 was generally well-correlated over time (SI Appendix, Tables S5 and S6), so we used an integrated
180 index of belowground biodiversity to evaluate changes in diversity with pedogenesis (see SI
181 Appendix, Material and Methods). This index was positively and significantly correlated with the
182 biodiversity of the major groups of organisms in >92% of the cases (59 out of 64 cases; SI
183 Appendix, Table S6). The strong positive correlation between soil bacteria, fungi, protists, and
184 invertebrates suggests that the changes in the biodiversity of multiple soil organisms during
185 pedogenesis are driven by similar ecological factors.

186 We then identified the form of the relationship between chronosequence stage and belowground
187 biodiversity within each chronosequence. For this, we considered the three most common
188 regression models used to evaluate changes in soil attributes during pedogenesis: linear, quadratic
189 and cubic (4-6,17,27; SI Appendix, Table S7 and Material and Methods). We found a high degree
190 of variation in the observed patterns across the 16 soil chronosequences (Fig. 2). In most cases,
191 belowground biodiversity took thousands to millions of years to reach its maximum as it followed
192 either positive (linear or cubic: seven cases) or hump-shaped (quadratic; five cases) relationships
193 with chronosequence stage (Fig. 2; SI Appendix, Figs. S5-S8 and Table S7). Changes in
194 belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis were not influenced by including chronosequences
195 of very different age ranges (from thousands to millions of years), as several patterns were found
196 within each soil age range (Fig. 2). We found similar results when evaluating the relationship
197 between chronosequence stage and the diversity of soil bacteria, fungi, protists and invertebrates
198 individually (SI Appendix, Figs S5-8 and Table S7). In support of this, the dissimilarity in
199 belowground community composition consistently increased with chronosequence stage (SI
200 Appendix, Table S8; Figs. S9-13), which suggests that belowground communities become more
201 dissimilar as pedogenesis proceeds. Further discussions about the changes in belowground
202 community composition during ecosystem development, based on the results reported below, are
203 available in SI Appendix, Extended Discussion.

204 Perennial plant diversity (plant diversity hereafter) was not correlated with belowground
205 biodiversity in 75% of the studied soil chronosequences (12 out of 16 cases; SI Appendix, Fig.
206 S14). Further, and unlike previously reported positive relationships between chronosequence stage
207 and plant diversity (4-6), we detected a high degree of variation in the responses of plant diversity
208 to pedogenesis (SI Appendix, Fig. S15; see Table S9 for the most important environmental factors
209 associated with perennial plant diversity). In particular, we found positive (25% of cases), negative
210 (18% of cases) and neutral (57% of cases) relationships between the diversity of plants and
211 belowground communities. Matching patterns of plant and soil biodiversity were not associated
212 with any particular type of ecosystem (SI Appendix, Table S9). In contrast to expectations (4-6),
213 which are largely developed from work on individual soil chronosequences typically located in
214 temperate environments, the observed changes in plant diversity during pedogenesis were highly
215 variable. We acknowledge that directly comparing patterns in the diversity of plants and soil

216 organisms is not straightforward due to differences in spatial scales, organism sizes, and taxonomic
217 resolution. Despite this important caveat, we still compared soil and plant diversity patterns during
218 pedogenesis (SI Appendix, Fig. S14 and S15 cf. Fig 2). Our findings challenge the common
219 expectation that belowground biodiversity mirrors aboveground diversity during pedogenesis
220 (4,9,16).

221 We then sought to identify the most important environmental factors associated with belowground
222 biodiversity across the 16 chronosequences studied (see Methods section). We first used Random
223 Forest modelling to identify those environmental factors that change during pedogenesis related
224 to each chronosequence (SI Appendix, Fig. S16). Environmental factors included aboveground
225 (plant cover) and belowground (soil total organic C and available P) resource availability, nutrient
226 stoichiometry (soil C:N and N:P ratios, calculated from soil total organic C, total N and total P)
227 and other soil abiotic factors (soil salinity, pH, and texture [% clay+silt]). These factors were then
228 selected as potential predictors of changes in belowground biodiversity and the diversity of
229 individual taxonomic groups during pedogenesis. Statistical modeling was always independently
230 conducted for each of the 16 soil chronosequences. A rationale on the inclusion of soil available P
231 and plant cover in our models is available in the SI Appendix, “Environmental predictors of
232 belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis”.

233 Our Random Forest analyses provided evidence that plant cover and soil pH are the most important
234 statistical predictors of changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis (Fig. 3; SI
235 Appendix, Figs. S17-S23). We then used hierarchical clustering to test the importance of
236 environmental factors in predicting belowground biodiversity (from Random Forest modeling) and
237 to classify our 16 soil chronosequences by the major ecological patterns associated with the
238 observed changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis. Most chronosequences were
239 clustered either by soil pH or plant cover (six out of 16 in both cases) as the major factors associated
240 with the changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis (Fig. 3; SI Appendix, Fig. S24).
241 Interestingly, on average, locations for chronosequences where belowground biodiversity was
242 associated with plant cover also had significantly lower ecosystem productivity and harsher
243 climatic conditions (lower temperature and precipitation) than those where belowground
244 biodiversity was associated with soil pH (SI Appendix, Fig. S25). In other words, soil
245 chronosequences where belowground biodiversity was positively correlated with plant cover had
246 lower ecosystem productivity, and corresponded with colder and drier ecosystems (SI Appendix,
247 Figs. S24-S25). In these ecosystems, increases in plant cover during pedogenesis were typically
248 associated with increases in belowground biodiversity (Figs 1B and 3; SI Appendix, Tables S10-
249 S11). The only exception to this pattern was a very old (millions of years) chronosequence located
250 in semi-arid grasslands from Colorado (CO), where a reduction in plant cover late in pedogenesis
251 was associated with reductions in belowground biodiversity (Figs 1B and 3).

252 Conversely, our findings indicate that, on average, chronosequences where soil pH was strongly
253 correlated with changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis had higher ecosystem
254 productivity corresponding with warmer and wetter ecosystems (SI Appendix, Figs. S24-S25). In
255 these ecosystems, declines in soil pH during pedogenesis were associated, in most cases (Fig. 3A),
256 with reductions in the number of soil taxa (Figs 1B and 3; SI Appendix, Tables S10-S11). This
257 pattern can likely be attributed to environmental filtering linked to soil acidification, which is a
258 result of intense weathering (Figs 1B, 3 and SI Appendix, Figs. S25-S26). Such a pattern has been
259 reported for another highly productive and wet chronosequence from New Zealand not included
260 in our study (16). The only exception to this pattern was observed in an ecosystem with very high

261 initial soil pH located in warm Mediterranean shrublands from Western Australia (WA). Alkaline
262 soils in young sand dunes (pH ~9) from this chronosequence support low belowground
263 biodiversity, explaining the increase in belowground biodiversity as pH declines during
264 pedogenesis (SI Appendix, Fig. S26). Thus, our results suggest that pH deviations away from
265 neutral are associated with decreased belowground biodiversity during ecosystem development,
266 supporting an overall hump-shaped relationship between soil pH and belowground diversity (Fig.
267 1B; SI Appendix, Fig. S26). Taken together, these findings reveal the prevalent patterns associated
268 with the changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis and across resource gradients
269 worldwide, and suggest that changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis are
270 predictable across major ecosystem types. We note that the observed soil biodiversity patterns
271 associated with changes in plant cover and pH can be found in soil chronosequences with very
272 different age ranges (Figs. 2 and 3), suggesting that the extent of change in these key factors, rather
273 than soil age *per se*, drive soil biodiversity during pedogenesis.

274 Our findings indicate that the fate of belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis is associated
275 with two major ecological factors across a wide range of globally-distributed ecosystem types and
276 environmental conditions: i) plant cover in less productive systems; and ii) acidification in more
277 productive systems. These results are valid for soil chronosequences with very different age ranges
278 (thousands to millions of years). Our results suggest that more productive, wetter and hotter
279 ecosystems can potentially limit the development of belowground biodiversity as a consequence
280 of the soil acidification associated with pedogenesis. Conversely, in low-productivity, colder and
281 drier ecosystems, plant cover was positively correlated with the changes in belowground
282 biodiversity during ecosystem development across multiple chronosequences with very different
283 age ranges. Of course, plants are not only a source of C for soil organisms (via litter and root
284 exudates) but also improve microclimatic conditions, especially in the low productivity
285 ecosystems often found in low temperature and/or arid climates (SI Appendix, Fig. S25). This
286 could explain, for instance, the reduction in belowground biodiversity at the CO chronosequence,
287 as plant cover declines with soil age in this relatively dry and cold region. In more productive
288 ecosystems (see SI Appendix, Fig. S25 for statistical support), acidification can potentially
289 constrain the diversity of soil organisms (SI Appendix, Fig. S26) via multiple interactive
290 mechanisms, including metal toxicity, solubility of essential nutrients, enzyme stability or internal
291 cell pH regulation. We also found two other less common patterns for the changes in belowground
292 biodiversity during pedogenesis. For instance, soil salinity was selected as the most important
293 environmental factor associated with the changes in belowground diversity during pedogenesis in
294 a non-saline (0.01-0.29 dS m⁻¹) temperate forest from Chile (CH, SI Appendix, Table S2).
295 Moreover, soil texture was selected as the most important environmental factor associated with
296 the changes in belowground diversity during ecosystem development in a temperate cropland
297 ecosystem with very high levels of silt and clay (79.5-86.4%) and very high potential weathering
298 rates (high levels of precipitation and temperature) (TA, SI Appendix, S25).

299 The observed correlation between soil pH and belowground biodiversity could be an indirect
300 consequence of reductions in soil P availability as soil develops (24-25), but our results suggest
301 otherwise. In fact, we expected soil C, N and P concentrations (or their stoichiometric ratios) to be
302 important factors associated with belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis because soil C is
303 a major energy source for heterotrophic microbes, and because resource quality (i.e., C:N and N:P)
304 and soil P concentrations are commonly considered limiting factors for belowground biodiversity
305 during pedogenesis (16,24-25). However, soil N:P ratio, soil total organic C concentration and soil
306 P availability were never selected as the most important factors associated with observed changes

307 in belowground diversity by our models (SI Appendix, Figs. S17-S18), and soil C:N ratio was only
308 selected as the most important environmental factor associated with a volcanic arid
309 chronosequence (BOV; SI Appendix, Table S2 and Fig. S27). More importantly, we conducted a
310 survey in a 27-year N and P fertilization experiment (25) and found that nutrient additions did not
311 increase belowground biodiversity in very young (0.3 ky; Stage 1 in our study) and very old (4100
312 ky; Stage 4 in our study) soils from Hawai'i (see SI Appendix, Fig. S28).

313 In summary, we found that plant cover and soil pH were the most important environmental factors
314 associated with changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis across a wide range of
315 globally-distributed ecosystem types. In less productive, drier and colder ecosystems increases in
316 plant cover during pedogenesis were related to increases in belowground biodiversity, whereas in
317 more productive ecosystems, which are also warmer and wetter, declines in soil pH during
318 pedogenesis were associated with declines in belowground diversity. Moreover, our results suggest
319 that the temporal changes in aboveground plant diversity and belowground biodiversity are not
320 correlated, challenging the common perception that belowground biodiversity should follow
321 similar patterns to those of plant diversity during ecosystem development. Our results also indicate
322 that we need to consider multiple soil chronosequences simultaneously to identify consistent
323 ecological patterns. Together, our findings provide novel insights into the fate of belowground
324 biodiversity during pedogenesis, and ultimately suggest that plant cover and soil acidification drive
325 belowground biodiversity over centuries to millennia on a global scale.

326 **Material and Methods**

327 Complete documentation of the study sites, field survey, sample collection, and laboratory
328 procedures, as well as additional details on the statistical analyses are provided in SI Appendix,
329 Materials and Methods. Field data were collected between 2016 and 2017 from 16 soil age
330 chronosequences located in nine countries from six continents (Fig. 1A). Each of the 16
331 chronosequences studied included between four and ten chronosequence age-based stages (SI
332 Appendix, Tables S2 and S3). At each stage, we conducted a vegetation survey and collected five
333 composite samples of mineral soil (five soil cores 0-10 cm deep, a total of 435 soil samples) and
334 obtained information on aboveground and belowground resource availability, nutrient
335 stoichiometry and other abiotic factors. The diversity of soil organisms was measured via marker
336 gene amplicon sequencing. Belowground biodiversity was calculated as the standardized average
337 of the diversity (i.e., richness; number of phylotypes) of soil bacteria, fungi, protists and
338 invertebrates. Detailed information on regression, Random Forest and hierarchical clustering
339 analyses can be found in the SI Appendix, Material and Methods.

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345 **Author contributions**

346 M.D-B. and N.F. developed the original idea of the analyses presented in the manuscript. M.D-B.
347 designed the field study and coordinated all field and laboratory operations. Field data were
348 collected by all authors except R.D.B., F.T.M. and N.F. Lab analyses were done by M.D-B., A.G.,

349 L.G-V. and F.T.M. Bioinformatic and statistical analyses were done by M.D-B. The paper was
350 written by M.D-B. and N.F with all authors contributing to the subsequent drafts.

351 **Data accessibility**

352 The primary data used in this paper have been deposited in figshare:
353 <https://figshare.com/s/0dc27c87f09d0a1c6ca3> (DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.7556675).

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Chronosequence origin \triangle Glacier \circ Volcanic **Soil age** \blacklozenge Millions of years
 ∇ Dunes \square Sedimentary \blacklozenge Hundreds thousand years
 \blacklozenge Thousand of years

424

425 **Figure 1. Geographical distribution and major patterns showing the fate of belowground**
 426 **biodiversity during pedogenesis.** Belowground biodiversity is defined as the standardized
 427 average of the diversity of soil bacteria, fungi, protists and invertebrates. Panel (a) shows the
 428 location of the 16 soil chronosequences (87 plots) included in this study. Panel (b) is a conceptual
 429 figure summarizing the major ecological patterns observed (see data in Figs. 2 and 3). Acronyms
 430 for each chronosequence are shown in SI Appendix, Table S2. See SI Appendix, Fig. S26 for
 431 correlations between pH and plant cover with belowground diversity across sites.

432

433 **Figure 2. Changes in belowground biodiversity during pedogenesis.** Relationship between
 434 chronosequence stage and belowground biodiversity across 16 globally distributed soil
 435 chronosequences.

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443 **Figure 3. Major ecological drivers of the fate of belowground biodiversity during**
 444 **pedogenesis.** Statistical support for these patterns are available in SI Appendix, Tables S10-S11.
 445 Numbers on panel C indicate the chronosequence stage. Arrows in the same panel indicate the
 446 overall directions for the changes in plant cover across stages. Changes in plant cover across
 447 chronosequence stages in this panel are calculated from stage 1 in each chronosequence.